

Guest Molecules in the Cages of Clathrate Hydrates: A Theoretical Study to Evaluate the Storage Capacity

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Abstract: Density functional theory (DFT) based studies are carried out to understanding structure, stability and reactivity of clathrate hydrates with or without hydrogen encapsulation. All geometries of clathrate hydrate were fully optimized using B3LYP/6-31G(d)//M06-2X/6-31G(d)//B97D/6-31G(d) level of theory. We systematically explore the gas capability of five standard water cavities (5^{12} , $4^35^66^3$, $5^{12}6^2$, $5^{12}6^4$ and $5^{12}6^8$) in clathrate hydrate. We have select for maximum cage occupancy of the five different cages (5^{12} , $4^35^66^3$, $5^{12}6^2$, $5^{12}6^4$ and $5^{12}6^8$) is one, two, three, four and five guest molecules in every cages. We used as a guest molecules Ar, CH₄, CO₂, H₂, H₂S, Kr, N₂, O₂ and Xe respectively. The maximum and optimum cage occupancy for all five considered cages as a guest molecule in the clathrate hydrate one, one, two, three, and four for CH₄, one, one, two, three, and four for CO₂, one, one, two, four and five for H₂, one, one, two, three, and four for O₂, one for all Xe, one, one, two, three, and four for Ar, one, one, two, three, and four for H₂S and one, one, two, three, and four for Kr. The efficacy of trapping of hydrogen molecules inside the cages of clathrate hydrates depends upon the cavity sizes and shapes of the clathrate hydrates. The efficacy of trapping of hydrogen molecules inside the cages of clathrate hydrates depends upon the cavity sizes and shapes of the clathrate hydrates.

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